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Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Practice and risk factors of zoonotic diseases among the Dairy farmers of Peri-urban areas: A – Cross-Sectional Study

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KEY HIGHLIGHTS

1. Despite India being a leading milk producer globally, there exists a significant lack of awareness among dairy farmers regarding Zoonotic diseases that lead to the burden.
2. This paper emphasizes the need to raise hygiene awareness among livestock caretakers, improving their knowledge regarding zoonotic infections.
3. Roadmap to Combat Zoonoses in India (RCZI) and the establishment of a One Health Consortium by the Department of Biotechnology under the Ministry of Science and Technology highlighted concerted efforts.
4. The dairy farming community needs a re-evaluation of healthcare systems, adopting an integrated One Health approach considering environmental, societal, economic, ethical, and political factors, despite gaps in disease surveillance and prevention.

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Zoonotic diseases are naturally transmitted infections between vertebrate animals and humans, impacting social, cultural, and economic development. India, the leading milk producer globally, faces significant health hazards due to a lack of awareness about milk-borne zoonosis and milking hygiene practices, highlighting the need for improved awareness and awareness-raising on zoonosis causes and impacts. The object of this paper was to assess the knowledge, practice, and attitude (KAPs) and risk factors of zoonotic disease among the dairy farmers of peri-urban areas. **MATERIALS AND METHODS:** The study design was cross-sectional and descriptive in

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nature. A total of 212 respondents were interviewed which included respondents more than 18 years old, milk suppliers from small dairy farms and distributors, and dairy farm workers who were directly involved in milking and handling of milk and milk products. The snowball sampling method was used. A Semi-structured questionnaire was designed to conduct interviews for data collection. This study has been conducted in Goyla Dairy, Dwarka division of South-West Delhi, India. **RESULTS:** This study of dairy farmers revealed a high level of education, extensive experience, and a strong bond between farmers and their livestock. A risk-scoring scale categorizes dairy farmers into low, moderate, and high-risk factor practices, with 41.51 percent in category 1, 38.68 percent in category 2, and 19.81 percent in category 3. **CONCLUSION:** Farmworker knowledge is adequate in certain areas but lacking in others, such as awareness of an illness that may be transmitted from cattle to people. Most dairy farmers engage in moderate to high-risk factor practices and there is a need to raise hygiene knowledge among livestock caretakers in terms of personal, animal, and milk cleanliness.

KEYWORDS: *Zoonotic Disease, Brucellosis, Bovine mastitis, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Risk factors and One Health*

BACKGROUND

India stands as the leading milk producer and boasting the highest number of dairy farmers. Despite the growing population and the rising demand for milk and dairy products, there is a lack of knowledge regarding the awareness of zoonotic disease risks among farmers, their preventive measures, and the extent of disease prevalence in animals. The World Health Organisation (WHO) has defined Zoonotic diseases as those diseases and infections, which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate's animals, and humans, and infections that are shared between vertebrates and humans. Zoonotic diseases have a significant effect on the social, cultural, and economic development of a country. In India, according to an international livestock research institute study, 13 zoonoses are caused by 2.4 billion cases of human disease and 2.2 million deaths per year (1). The highest zoonotic disease burden with widespread disease burden is in Ethiopia, Nigeria, Tanzania, and India(2). Climate change and global warming impact animal diversity, causing zoonoses. Favourable climatic, demographic, and socioeconomic conditions increase the probability of infectious epidemics in India (3). Diseases impact animal production, causing slow growth and reduced milk production, negatively impacting rural communities. With zoonotic diseases being positively related, disease ignorance has an adverse effect on both animal and human health.

The health risks stemming from a lack of awareness regarding the origins and consequences of zoonoses for public health are substantial. Furthermore, there appears to be a noticeable lack of emphasis on One-Health initiatives in India. Dairy farmers face ongoing challenges due to the lasting impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, adding to the existing concerns regarding diseases like brucellosis and bovine mastitis (4). Over the past two years, the world has grappled with the effects of COVID-19, highlighting the need for better disease prevention strategies. The rise of new diseases and the resurgence of old ones, such as brucellosis, have become more frequent, emphasizing the urgency for improved healthcare approaches(5).

Research has shown that preventing diseases like brucellosis is much more cost-effective than managing their widespread effects later, particularly when considering the global scale (6)(7). To protect the dairy farming community from such diseases, there's a pressing need to reevaluate healthcare systems. This re-evaluation requires a comprehensive understanding of disease emergence and the adoption of an integrated One Health approach that considers various factors—such as the environment, society, economy, ethics, and politics—impacting disease spread. However, despite discussions around a unified One Health approach by governments, the pandemic revealed significant gaps in disease surveillance and prevention (8). Drawing from this experience, this paper aimed to assess the

knowledge, attitudes, and practices of livestock farmers residing in Goyla Dairy, Dwarka, New Delhi regarding zoonotic diseases. This study enrolled farmers who were engaged in dairy farming on day-to-day basis and used questionnaire data to create three index variables of knowledge attitude and practice.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This study was carried out in South-West Delhi's Goyla Dairy division in Dwarka. This was a Cross-sectional descriptive study, and the duration of the study was three months (August-October 2023). The people who worked with cattle for the longest duration and who were actively involved in milking and handling milk products made up the study population. A total of 212 respondents were interviewed during data collection with the use of a convenience sampling process. The study had three inclusion criteria which included: the respondents more than 18 years old, milk suppliers from small dairy farms, and distributors and Dairy farm workers those were directly involved in the milking and handling of milk and milk products. The study had three exclusion criteria which was-respondent less than 18 years old, participants who do not have cattle and elderly members and children who are not involved in dairy farming practices. The snowball sampling method was used to attain the desired number of samples. Firstly, team identified 2-4 dairy farmers, and further the participants were asked to give information about similar subjects, and this was continued till achieved the desired sample size. The data were collected through interviews with the help of a questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of both open-ended questions and closed-ended questions. Semi-structured questions were divided into different sections; these sections included questions regarding, the knowledge and attitude of the dairy farmers, various animal husbandry practices, such as vaccination of cattle, sleeping in proximity with cattle, handling of aborted material, contact of cattle with other animals during grazing, it also included questions on socio-demographic details. Before analysis could begin, the data were edited, checked for accuracy, completeness, consistency, and omission, and organized to allow for coding and tabulation. Tables and graphs

were used to depict the percentages after the SAS was used for the analysis. Additionally, risk was scored on a scale of 0–14, where “0” denoted “no risk” and “14” denoted “on high risk.” This system was used for the 39 variables, 14 of which dealt with risk practices. A score of 1 was awarded for each dangerous behavior the respondent engaged in, which increases the likelihood of spreading the disease; a score of 0 was awarded for engaging in healthy behaviour. The project was approved by the Student Institutional Review Board of The International Institute of Health Management Research. Prior to the trial, the subjects gave their informed consent. In addition, the respondents were made aware of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any moment, confidentiality, and voluntary participation.

RESULTS

A total of 212 dairy farmers were interviewed, about 19.81 percent of respondents got primary education and 26.41 percent of respondents acquired secondary education among all dairy farmers. It was found that the cattle rearing responsibilities were mostly done by the workers (57%). The responses were divided into 3 parts, knowledge, practice, and attitude regarding the risk factors of zoonotic diseases.

Among the surveyed respondents, 92.92 percent were male, and a substantial portion were female farmers, constituting 7.08 percent. Educational qualifications varied significantly within the community, with 10.85 percent holding formal education beyond high school. Furthermore, dairy farmers having experience in dairy farming for 5 or more years are 73.58 percent, highlighting the wealth of practical knowledge within this community. An intriguing aspect emerged regarding sleeping arrangements, with 27.83 percent of respondents reporting habitual nights spent in the barn alongside their cattle. Additionally, the housing of cattle revealed that a considerable portion of the population, approximately 99.06 percent, keeps their cattle under roofed structures. These figures shed light on the intimate connection between dairy farmers and their livestock, impacting daily practices and potential exposure to zoonotic diseases.

Table 1:- Demographic characteristics of cattle farmers in the urban and peri-urban area of Goyla Dairy, Delhi (N=212)

Particulars	Range	Frequency	(%)
Age	18-25	57	26.88
	26-30	39	19.39
	31-35	18	8.49
	36-40	21	9.90
	41 and above	77	36.32
Education	No Schooling	91	42.92
	Up to Primary (1 to 5)	42	19.18
	Up to Middle (6 to 8)	32	15.09
	Up to High School (9 to 10)	24	11.32
	Up to Senior Secondary (11 to 12)	11	5.19
	Graduation	5	19.11
	Post Graduation and Higher	1	0.47
Experience	1-5	56	26.42
	5-10	82	38.68
	10-15	52	24.53
	Above 15 years	22	10.38
Income	Less than 5000	1	0.47
	Rs 5001-10000	2	0.94
	Rs 10001-15000	101	47.64
	Rs 15001-20000	64	30.19
	Rs 20001-25000	17	8.02
	Rs 25001-30000	10	4.72
	Rs 30001 and above	17	8.02
Daily average milk production	0-30	18	8.49
	30-60	50	23.58
	60-90	52	24.52
	Above 90	92	43.39
Lactating cattle number	Less than 10	26	12.26
	10-20	79	37.26
	20-30	40	18.86
	Above 30	67	31.60

Table 2:- Knowledge about Zoonotic disease among the respondents who had heard of the disease in the urban and peri-urban area of Goyla Dairy, Delhi (N=212)

Indicators	Range	Frequency	(%)
Importance of pasteurization of milk.	Yes	109	51.42
Disease can transfer from cattle to humans	No	151	71.23
Knowledge about some of the diseases that can transfer from cattle to humans	Brucellosis	15	24.59
	Bovine Mastitis	32	52.46
	Tuberculosis	5	8.2

Table 3:- Attitude about Zoonotic disease among the respondents who had heard of the disease in the urban and peri-urban area of Goyla Dairy, Delhi (N=212)

Indicators	Category	Frequency	(%)
Thinking that training for cattle rearing should be given by government	Yes	115	54.25
Taking cattle to the veterinary	Yes	118	55.66
	No	1	0.47
	Use home remedies.	14	6.60
	Only when it is very urgent.	79	37.26

Most of the people knew about the disease transmission pathways from animal to humans due to the proximity with cattle. So, they do the pasteurizing the milk and most of the respondents took cattle to the veterinarian when fall seek.

Risk Score

Risk scoring was done on a scale of 3 from low to high. 1 for low-risk factor practices, 2 for moderate-risk factor practices, and 3 for high-risk factor practices. From the questionnaire 14 such variables were selected for creating a composite indicator of the risk factor practices, like sleeping in close contact with cattle, assistance during reproduction without protective gloves, contact with other cattle during grazing, improper and irregular vaccination, consumption of raw milk and urine, no proper cleanliness of utensils, not keeping cattle under roof, unhygienic milking practices like dirty hands and udder during milking, using infected milk, no regular barn cleaning.

The composite indicator is then divided into 3 tertiles, with tertile points at 33.33 percent and 66.67 percent. Percentage distribution of risk scoring is 41.51 percent of dairy farmers are in category 1, following 0-2 risk factor practices, 38.68 percent of dairy farmers falls

under category 2, with 3-4 risk factor practices and 19.81 percent of dairy farmers falls under category 3, following 5 or more risk factors practices.

Table 4:- Practice and Risk among the respondents in the urban and peri-urban area .

Indicator	Category	Frequency	%
Sleeping near cattle	Yes	59	27.83
Contact with other livestock	Yes	13	6.13
Regular vaccination of cattle	Yes	159	75.00
Assistance during reproduction using protective gear.	Yes	85	40.09
Consumption of raw milk	Yes	47	22.17
Washing udder before milking	Yes	203	95.75
Using clean utensils	Yes	194	91.51
Keeping cattle in barn with roof	Yes	210	99.06

Drying hand before milking	Yes	103	48.58
Drying udder after washing	Yes	95	44.81
Using infected milk (Milk with clots and flakes)	Yes	61	28.77
Cleaning barn more than once in a day	Yes	205	96.70
Using soap before or after milking	Yes	208	98.11

Table 5:- Risk Score

Indicator	Category	Frequency	%
Categorized risk score	High	42	41.51
	Moderate	82	38.68
	Low	42	19.81
Risk Factor practices	0 risk factor practices	13	6.13
	1 risk factor practice	39	18.40
	2 risk factor practices	36	16.98
	3 risk factor practices	39	18.40
	4 risk factor practices	43	20.28
	5 risk factor practices	30	14.15
	6 risk factor practices	8	3.77
7 risk factor practices	4	1.89	

DISCUSSION

For numerous households, especially those who own cattle, livestock serves as a supplemental source of income in India. However, many households have a primary source of Income. Those who raise livestock are vital to the economies of all nations, but this is particularly true of developing nations like India. In the Peri Urban area of Delhi, India, this paper addressed the livestock farmers' knowledge, attitudes, practices, as well as understanding of zoonotic diseases. The study findings showed that, in the Indian state of Delhi, the majority of farmers were uninformed of the spread, treatment, and prevention of zoonosis such bovine mastitis and brucellosis (9). Across all of these research, it has been observed that raising awareness of the value of hygiene among stakeholders is crucial for improving knowledge, fostering positive attitudes, and promoting appropriate hygiene practices among milk handlers at

all levels (10)(11). Although education has a good impact on the knowledge levels of respondents, there is still a problem in improving the breadth and depth of information related zoonotic illnesses (12). This suggests that more thorough teaching methods or materials are required.

A majority of the farmers did not use protective gloves when dealing with cows having an abortion or with aborted materials. One explanation for this could be poor knowledge of the risk with this practice but also lack of access to protective gears like gloves.

Discussing animal health problems with veterinarians was almost as common as doing so with family members or friends. When cows exhibited signs of illness, the majority of farmers sought the expertise of a veterinarian. This pattern aligns with the results of a study, where most participants indicated a preference for contacting local veterinarians when suspecting brucellosis infection in their livestock (13). The current study revealed that participants who primarily sought advice from veterinarians regarding animal health matters were more likely to be aware of brucellosis compared to those who primarily consulted family members or friends. The well-established rapport between veterinarians and farmers could prove beneficial when implementing information campaigns as part of a future control program. Moreover, generational or cultural beliefs could render it more challenging to implement suggested behaviors. Additionally, there is a pressing need to create comprehensive diagnostic techniques and improved surveillance systems in order to increase understanding of zoonotic illnesses and surveillance mechanisms.

In India, there are concerted national endeavors aimed at prioritizing zoonotic diseases for research and control, exemplified by initiatives like the Roadmap to Combat Zoonoses in India (RCZI) (14). This strategic plan identifies key zoonotic diseases warranting research emphasis in the coming decade. Additionally, the Department of Biotechnology under the Ministry of Science and Technology has initiated a One Health Consortium. This consortium is primarily dedicated to comprehensive surveillance of significant bacterial, viral, and parasitic infections, including both zoonotic and transboundary pathogens (15). India's efforts to combat zoonotic diseases align with global initiatives addressing these health concerns. Sustained emphasis on research, surveillance, education, and collaborative endeavors will play a pivotal role in reducing the risks

associated with zoonotic diseases, ensuring the well-being of both humans and animals.

CONCLUSION

Milk is a necessary product that a significant number of people consume. Maintaining quality is critical from both a health and economic standpoint. The study concludes that animal husbandry practices such as keeping animals close to humans during sleep, irregular vaccination of cattle, sharing water sources, treating animals on their own when they become ill, and assistance during reproduction without wearing protective gloves contribute to the risk of brucellosis, and defects in foremilk such as blood, flakes, clots, and redness in the udder contribute to the risk factor of bovine mastitis among the cattle. According to the findings of this study, most dairy farmers engage in moderate to high-risk factor practices. Furthermore, there is a need to raise hygiene knowledge among livestock caretakers in terms of personal, animal, and milk cleanliness.

A critical examination of the data revealed that farmworkers perform a few practises such as keeping cattle in a barn with a roof, washing and drying hands before and after milking, cleaning utensils before and after milking, filtering milk before use, and immunisation of cattle. Few actions, such as washing the floor with detergents, drying the udder before milking, and correct dung utilisation or disposal, are practised seldom.

Farmworker knowledge is adequate in certain areas but lacking in others, such as awareness of illnesses that may be transmitted from cattle to people. However, it is critical to develop minimum criteria that should reach the ground level worker and be properly enforced. Public health professionals should train them and check their practises on a regular basis so that they are better knowledgeable about zoonotic infections. Small attempts in this area can safeguard society from different zoonotic infections and health difficulties by consuming milk. Zoonotic infections are widespread and frequently overlooked in underdeveloped nations, even though they have serious public health repercussions. These must be incorporated into health policy and prevention measures. For its surveillance in humans and animals, there should be intersectoral coordination. The risk variables for infection transmission should be identified and communicated to the risk population in animal fairs and camps. As a result, the study recommends that a

One-Health strategy be used when dealing with zoonoses, as other stakeholders, particularly veterinary specialists, have a significant role in bringing about changes in livestock safety.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

SK, AR, JR, MS and SS conceptualized and designed the study. AR, JR, SK, MS, and KS designed study tool, collected data, analyzed and interpreted the data, and drafted the manuscript. SS contributed to the thorough review and editing of the final manuscript. All the authors provided critical input on the paper, read and approved the final paper. SS takes responsibility as a guarantor for this research article.

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AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by the International Institute of Health Management (IIHMR) student research board.

Informed Consent

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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